

Soundful Dickens The Narrative Functions of Sounds in Dickens's Fictional Worlds

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Introduction

But there was nothing on the back of the door except the screws and nuts that held the knocker on
<character_sound>so he said</character_sound> "Pooh pooh!" <ambient_sound>and closed it with a
bang</ambient_sound>. <ambient_sound>The sound resounded through the house like thunder</ambient_sound>.

Example 1: Extract of Dickens's *A Christmas Carol*.

Sound as a narratological phenomenon has gained increasing attention in recent years. Especially within traditional literary studies, works by Picker (2003), Glotova (2021), Molyneux (2022), and Foley (2024) have paved the way for textual research on soundscapes. Accordingly, passages like the one in the opening sample can be analysed in a close reading approach to look for sounds by characters as well as ambient sounds in the fictional worlds.

Operationalisation of Fictional Sound

Guhr's (2026) operationalisation of fictional sounds for automated recognition and classification opens new avenues for the computational analysis of soundscapes and the scalable reading of the sonic dimensions of literary fiction. Focusing on the representation of sounds in the narration like "banging doors" can be operationalised as fictional sound events. These events are sound-word-bearing syntactic phrases that can be labelled with loudness levels. Following the event-based model developed by Gius and Vauth (2021), Guhr (2026) systematically annotated literary prose texts for sound events and labelled them with loudness levels based on a dictionary-matching algorithm. Following her annotation guidelines, the opening Example 1 contains three sound events that can be classified as either 'charac-

ter' or 'ambient sounds', with the source of the sound being either a character or something else classified in the 'ambient sound' default category. The passage includes the character sound event "so he said" (loudness level 3), as well as the ambient sound events "closed it with a bang" (loudness level 4), and "[t]he sound resounded through the house like thunder" (loudness level 4.5). The loudness annotation is independent of the sound source's spatial distance. Instead, loudness levels are assigned by matching sound-denoting words to entries in a predefined loudness dictionary (e.g. {'said': 3, 'bang': 5, 'thunder': 5}), in which each lexical item is associated with a numeric loudness value (from very low (1) to very loud (5) sounds). When a sound event contains multiple sound words, the final loudness label is calculated as the average of the corresponding dictionary values.

Guhr originally developed her approach for German-language fiction. This paper presents an extension of the annotation scheme to British English, which we illustrate with a use case of texts by Charles Dickens. The adaptation of the methodology follows a novel approach that leverages the capabilities of modern machine translation: instead of relying exclusively on manual annotation of the English texts, we hypothesised that machine-translated versions of the German-language XML-annotations (here using the DeepL API (2024)) offer valid training data to finetune a pre-trained English-language BERT model (Devlin et al. 2019, model from 2024).

«Unbegreiflich! Die Sache liegt ja gar nicht in seiner Kompetenz!» <character_sound loudness="4">rief der Gouverneur</character_sound>. Auch der Oberst fand die Sache so auffällig als traurig. Er entfernte sich indeß wiederum bald <character_sound loudness="3">und der Gouverneur befahl</character_sound>, daß man sein Pferd sattele.

"Incomprehensible! The matter is not within his competence!" <character_sound loudness="4">cried the governor</character_sound>. The colonel, too, found the matter as striking as it was sad. He soon departed again <character_sound loudness="3">and the governor ordered</character_sound> his horse to be saddled.

Example 2: Comparison of a German original text extract of Auerbach's *Auf Wache* and its automatically generated British English translation.

While Guhr's (2024) finetuned German BERT model (Chan et al. 2020, Lemke et al. 2023) required 55 annotated prose texts (667,665 words, 9,831 annotations; E-F1-Score: 0.7, precision: 0.66, recall: 0.68, F1-score: 0.67), the more powerful English-language model already demonstrated promising performance when finetuned on only five annotated prose texts (50,804 words, 1,046 annotations; E-F1-Score: 0.65, precision: 0.54, recall: 0.62, F1-score: 0.58; The test set contained 6,212 words with 125 sound annotations from randomly collected passages of further five Dickens's novels).

The English training set contained one manually annotated English-language text, Dickens's *A Christmas Carol*, and four texts of medium length chosen from the German-language training set provided by Guhr (2024) that were automatically translated into British English using the DeepL API (DeepL SE, 2024). Thanks to the XML TEI markup, the translation model was forced to translate the already annotated sound-event spans as coherent units, preserving their internal boundaries during translation (see Example 2). This constraint, however, applies only to the

preparation of the training data and not to the subsequent prediction step. In an error analysis of randomly chosen samples of sound-predicted passages, we found that the model performs particularly well in recognising the presence of a sound event, but often predicts imprecise or fragmented spans in unseen texts. However, due to the small training set and following the procedure by Guhr (2026), the boundary errors were addressed by a regular expression-based post-processing step to prepare the model output for analysis.

To compare translated and original language training data, we conducted two experiments: firstly, we created a new training set using the existing model for the pre-annotation of two original British English texts and manually corrected the model output. The training set contains Lewis’ *The Anaconda*, Gaskell’s *The Old Nurses Story*, and Dickens’s *A Christmas Carol* (62,462 words), as in the initial experiment. Secondly, we combined the two training sets ((a) with and (b) without translations), resulting in a training set of seven sound-annotated texts, containing the four controlled machine-translated ones, the two newly corrected original British texts, and *A Christmas Carol* (in the following CC).

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Gold annotations
Many and many a time, in the day and in the night, with my head upon the pillow by her that my whispers might be plainer to her, I kissed her, <character_sound>thanked her/<character_sound>, <character_sound>prayed for her/<character_sound>, <character_sound>asked her for her blessing and forgiveness/<character_sound>, <character_sound>entreated her/<character_sound> to give me the least sign that she knew or heard me.

BE_with_translations
Many and many a time, in the day and in the night, with my head upon the pillow by her that my whispers might be plainer to her, <character_sound>I/<character_sound> kissed <character_sound>her/<character_sound>, <character_sound>thanked her/<character_sound>, <character_sound>prayed for her/<character_sound>, <character_sound>asked her for her blessing and forgiveness/<character_sound>, <character_sound>entreated her/<character_sound> to give me the least sign that she knew or heard me.

BE_no_translations
Many and many a time, in the day and in the night, with my head upon the pillow by her that my whispers might be plainer to her, I kissed <character_sound>her/<character_sound>, <character_sound>thanked her/<character_sound>, <character_sound>prayed <character_sound>for her/<character_sound>, <character_sound>asked her for her blessing and forgiveness/<character_sound>, <character_sound>entreated <character_sound>her/<character_sound> to give me the least sign that she knew or heard me.

BE_mixed_training_set
Many and many a time, in the day and in the night, with my head upon the pillow by her that my whispers might be plainer to her, I kissed <character_sound>her/<character_sound>, <character_sound>thanked her/<character_sound>, <character_sound>prayed <character_sound>for her/<character_sound>, <character_sound>asked her for her blessing and forgiveness/<character_sound>, <character_sound>entreated her/<character_sound> to give me the least sign that she knew or heard me.
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Example 3: Comparison of the outputs of the three models prior postprocessing of an extract from Dickens’s Bleak House.

We then compared the performance of the three models (see Table 1): although the model fine-tuned on the machine-translations and CC achieved higher evaluation scores, a qualitative comparison of the model outputs against the gold standard revealed a discrepancy between quantitative performance and annotation quality. The model finetuned on translated data (prior to postprocessing) tends to maximise recall by producing a large number of short and fragmented sound spans, frequently annotating pronouns, conjunctions, or other function words in the vicinity of sound events.

This behaviour is illustrated in Example 3. Compared to the gold annotations, the translation-based model produces additional annotations, including false positives such as the pronoun-only spans “I” and “her”, while correctly identifying the sound-event sequences “prayed for her” and “entreated her”. By contrast, the model fine-tuned exclusively on original British English texts produces less annotations but exhibits several near-misses: it marks fragments such as “for her” and “her”, but fails to annotate the corresponding sound verbs “prayed” and “entreated”. As a result, both mo-

dels partially overlap with the gold standard yet differ in the semantic coherence of their predicted spans.

These fragmentary overlaps are only weakly penalised by commonly used evaluation metrics, which explains why the translation-based model attains comparatively high scores despite reduced interpretability of its annotations. The model trained solely on original English texts, in contrast, produces fewer false positives and more coherent annotation units, but underperforms quantitatively due to a higher rate of missed sound events, as again evidenced in Example 3. This divergence highlights a systematic mismatch between standard span-based evaluation metrics and human-interpretable annotation quality in sound-event detection.

In line with previous findings that increased training data generally improves detection performance (Guhr 2026), the third experiment combining translated and original English training data yielded the best overall results, balancing robust sound-event detection with improved span coherence.

The overall results suggest that machine translated annotations may be a valid addition to training data opening new opportunities for re-using data sets. At the same time, the translation of annotations raises questions that deserve to be further investigated in the context of translation studies. Especially the fact that the model trained on English originals had a higher rate of missed sound events might relate to effects of simplification that have been shown to occur in translations (cf. eg. Baker 1996).

BE sound event models	texts	words	annotations	E-F1-Score	precision	recall	F1-score
training set with translations	5	58,804	1,046	0.65	0.54	0.62	0.58
training set without translations	3	62,462	1,066	0.62	0.52	0.54	0.53
mixed training set	7	82,999	1,464	0.66	0.55	0.61	0.58

Table 1: Evaluation results of the three different models calculated in NEISS NTEE (Lemke et al. 2023).

Sound in *A Christmas Carol*

In this section, we will have a closer look at Dickens’s *A Christmas Carol* (CC) to see how the quantification of sound patterns can provide entry points for detailed textual analysis. Figure 1 shows the loudness averages for CC and Dickens’s 15 novels (texts retrieved from a collection of reformatted texts for use with corpus linguistic tools provided by the Mahlberg-Lab (2019) at: <https://github.com/mahlberg-lab/corpora>). Overall, across all novels, the average ambient loudness is higher than the character average loudness. This makes sense since ambient sound can refer to the sound of groups of characters as well as non-human sounds.

Figure 1: Loudness averages and standard deviation for CC and DNov.

When it comes to the proportion of ambient vs character sound types, the situation is the other way round. Character sounds make up a higher proportion than ambient sounds. It is important to note that the distinction between ambient and character sounds is not to be understood in terms of the distinction between actual character speech and narration. Even ‘character’ sounds are typically described by the narrator, as in Example 1 above, where “so he said” is annotated as character sound.

Figure 2: Proportion of ambient vs character sounds in CC.

Overviews such as Figure 1 make it possible to compare the soundscapes of different texts. The quantitative data can then form the basis for a more detailed textual analysis. Figure 1 shows that *CC* has the highest average character loudness; also for the ambient sounds *CC* scores relatively highly. We used Dickens’s *CC* as text to manually annotate, because it is relatively short, compared to Dickens’s novels (*DNov*). Apart from *CC*, all texts in Figure 1 are novels. The novella is not only markedly shorter, but it also has a more straightforward story. In the subtitle of *CC*, Dickens refers to it as a ghost story, and with the focus on the transformation of Scrooge this story has a very clear moral message. Dickens is not very subtle in his portrayal of the transformation of the main character and the soundscape of the text underlines the main message. There are two main textual functions of sound patterns in *CC*: sounds signal the structure of the story in terms of time and sounds support the contrast between Scrooge, the unhappy miser,

and the cheerful people who enjoy Christmas. Examples of the ambient vocabulary that have a structural function are *bell/bells*, *chime/chimes*, *clock/clocks*, *struck/stroke*. In Example 4, the sound of *bells* foreshadows the arrival of Marley’s ghost. The repetition of the word *bell* further emphasises the build-up of the sound that is then followed by the clanking of the ghost’s chain.

As he threw his head back in the chair, his glance happened to rest upon a bell, a disused bell, that hung in the room, and communicated for some purpose now forgotten with a chamber in the highest story of the building. It was with great astonishment, and with a strange, inexplicable dread, that as he looked, he saw this bell begin to swing. It swung so softly in the outset <ambient_sound>that it scarcely made a sound</ambient_sound>; <ambient_sound>but soon it rang out loudly</ambient_sound>; <ambient_sound>and so did every bell in the house</ambient_sound>.

Example 4: Extract from Dickens’s *CC*.

Throughout the story the ghostly appearances are accompanied by appropriately ghostly sounds. Time plays an important role in the story as Marley’s ghost warns Scrooge to use his time to change and avoid the same fate as Marley. The marking of time – supported by sound – underlines the progression of the story, which is further structured by the appearance of the three Spirits. In chapter 3, when Scrooge is visited by the second Spirit, who tells him that he has only got till midnight until he will leave again, the text stresses how time runs out, again marked by sound, as in “<ambient_sound>The chimes were ringing the three quarters past eleven at that moment</ambient_sound>.” “And the Spirit disappears at the stroke of midnight: “<ambient_sound>The bell struck twelve</ambient_sound>. Scrooge looked about him for the Ghost, and saw it not.”

The focus on time is also used to show Scrooge’s transformation. At the end of the story, it is not the ghostly visit that the striking of the clock marks, but time is used to show how Scrooge has changed. The newly-transformed Scrooge is waiting for his clerk Bob, so that he can surprise him and raise his salary. Time now works differently: “<ambient_sound>The clock struck nine</ambient_sound>. No Bob. A quarter past. No Bob. He was full eighteen minutes and a half behind his time.”

The other textual function of sound patterns is the contrast between the miserable Scrooge and the cheerful people who celebrate Christmas. The holiday season is accompanied by music, singing and laughter, all sounds that belong to people who enjoy each other’s company, as opposed to Scrooge who stays away from the festivities and dismisses them as a “humbug.”

Local sound patterns in *Dombey and Son*

The annotation of sounds as character and ambient sounds suggests that ‘sound’ is a relatively straightforward category. However, the depiction of sounds can create a variety of textual effects. The textual patterns of sound fulfil what Mahlberg (2013) refers to as ‘local textual functions’. We can already illustrate such local functions by comparing the textual effects of the sound of bells in *CC* and in *Dombey*

and *Son* (*DS*). In *CC*, the sound patterns are specific to the text but they are very clear throughout. In the novel *DS*, the patterns are more complex. Figure 1 above might suggest that in *DS* sound is less relevant than in the other texts. But closer inspection reveals that the textual functions associated with the sound vocabulary are more localized. Figure 3 shows the distribution of sound events across chapters in *DS*. With this view, chapter 55 stands out as a place that has relatively more ambient sounds than all other chapters. As in *CC*, we also find bells in chapter 55 of *DS*. In some way similarly to *CC*, the bells are associated with textual patterns that show how a character experiences a sense of haunting. In *DS*, bells are part of the repeated phrase “the monotony of bells and wheels, and horses’ feet, and no rest” that relates to Carker’s anxiety in the course of his desperate attempt to flee his past. Carker’s flight ends with him being hit by a train. In the chapter, the description of sounds contributes to depicting Carker’s mental state. At the same time, the sounds accompany the build-up to the end of a chapter that Zullo (2020: 88) aptly characterises as “the soundscape of Carker’s tremendous end”.

Figure 3: Sound events per chapter in *DS* with peak of ambient sounds in chapter 55.

Conclusions

This study demonstrates how fictional sounds can be systematically recognised, classified, and analysed in literary texts using a computational approach that adapts and extends Guhr's (2026) sound event operationalisation to English-language fiction. Even with a small training set, the results show that meaningful insights into the distribution, type, and loudness of fictional sounds can be extracted, enabling scalable analysis of fictional soundscapes.

In Dickens's *CC* in particular, sound plays a prominent narrative role, structuring time, signalling ghostly, supernatural presence, and contributing to the depiction of character contrasts and developments. Our examples illustrate how the visualisation of sound type distributions provides new entry points for interpretation and opens possibilities for comparative soundscape studies across genres and periods.

Future work will integrate sound annotation with scene segmentation (Zehe et al., 2025) from which we hope to gain more detailed insights into scenes with curious loudness level profiles, highlighting passages for close reading. The current method does not yet account for effects of local sound repetitions, as seen in *DS*, nor for the stylistic dimensions of sound usage, both of which future research will address.

Code and data: https://github.com/SvenjaGuhr/Literary_Soundscapes.

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